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Psychological Study of the Etiology of Intellectual Disability

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Abstract: *The etiology of intellectual disability is of significant importance in clinical psychology and developmental psychology. The psychology of intellectually disabled children also heavily relies on advances in psychiatry. Collaborative research between psychiatrists and educators has led to the development of criteria for the pedagogical and psychological diagnosis of intellectual disability. Regardless of the degree of intellectual disability, cognitive development is influenced by the extent of brain damage.*

Key words: *Etiology, Physiology, Neuropathology, Psychiatry, Pathogenesis, Clinical Trauma, Asphyxia, Infections, Intoxications.*

The etiology of intellectual disability is varied. It can result from genetic disorders of the central nervous system due to trauma, asphyxia, infections, and intoxications that occur during pregnancy, childbirth, or early developmental stages. The clinical description of the main forms of intellectual disability is closely tied to the timing of the traumatic event and the pathogenetic impact of the negative influence. If the central nervous system is damaged during the early stages of ontogenesis (up to 2 years of age), the formation of the cerebral cortex is primarily affected, leading to underdevelopment. This results in various forms of oligophrenia. In cases where brain damage occurs at a more mature stage of cortical development, various forms of dementia predominate.

Advancements in research methods have highlighted the importance of genetic factors in the etiology of intellectual disability. Various chromosomal abnormalities are implicated in genetic forms of oligophrenia, such as changes in chromosome number, structural alterations, deletions, translocations, and morphological changes. The causes of these chromosomal abnormalities are diverse and not fully understood, but may include factors such as incomplete development of generative cells in parents, exposure to chemical substances, chronic diseases, and radiation. The second group of genetically-induced oligophrenia is related to enzymatic defects that disrupt metabolic processes. Disorders like phenylketonuria, galactosemia, and others are becoming increasingly recognized as causes of intellectual disability. These conditions are characterized by the congenital absence of specific

enzymes, leading to the accumulation of toxic substances in the body, which adversely affect brain development. Intellectual disability can also have exogenous causes, such as negative external influences on the developing fetus during pregnancy. Chronic and acute infectious diseases, exposure to harmful chemicals, and certain medications taken by the mother can result in forms of oligophrenia. Radiological exposure also poses a pathogenic risk to the fetus. Additionally, maternal health conditions such as endocrine disorders and vitamin deficiencies can contribute to fetal pathology. The study of the etiology of intellectual disability benefits significantly from psychological sciences. Neuropathology provides insights into the anatomical and organic disturbances of the central nervous system in intellectually disabled children, while physiology offers information about the functional disturbances. This knowledge enhances our understanding of the mental deficiencies in intellectually disabled children. The psychology of these children builds on the physiological teachings of I.P. Pavlov regarding the plasticity of the central nervous system. Intellectually disabled children's psychology also fully utilizes advances in psychiatry. Pioneers like G.Y. Sukhareva and M.S. Pevzner have made substantial contributions to the clinical study of intellectually disabled children, examining the etiology, pathogenesis, treatment, and secondary complications of their conditions. Through collaboration between psychiatrists and educators, criteria for the pedagogical and psychological diagnosis of intellectual disability have been established. Given the shared principles of normal and impaired child development, it is essential to understand the unique aspects of intellectually disabled children's development, which is guided by general psychological and social psychology principles, as well as the achievements in developmental psychology.

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